

POLAND

POLAND

INNOVATIONS AND ADVANCED FOREIGN EXPERIENCES IN TEACHING SPECIALIZED SUBJECTS

Mallaboyev Nosirjon Murodullayevich

Associate Professor of Namangan Engineering and Construction Institute

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8006042>

Abstract: One of the main goals of the reforms implemented in our country is to create new economic relations based on the laws of the market economy and to create a legislative base aimed at their consistent legal regulation. As stated in the national personnel training program, "Man, his all-round harmonious growth and well-being, creation of conditions and effective mechanisms for the realization of personal interests, change of outdated patterns of thinking and social behavior are the economic activities implemented in the Republic is the main goal and driving force of reforms. "Formation of an excellent system of personnel training based on the rich intellectual heritage of the people, universal values, and the achievements of modern culture, economy, science, technology and technology is an important condition for the development of Uzbekistan."

Keywords: information technologies, higher education, intellectual potential and intelligence.

Reforming and improving the education system of Uzbekistan in the 21st century is one of the priority tasks. This, in turn, is the responsibility of our scientists to update the educational literature in the relevant academic subjects, taking into account the requirements of the current period and the latest achievements of science, to introduce innovation and educational technologies into the educational process. is demanding. It is known that the application of innovations and advanced foreign experiences in the process of teaching "Distributed Systems" in the higher educational institutions of our country is one of the urgent issues of today. First of all, what is new in science? It is necessary to answer the questions of what is innovation in science. Today, in practice, there are differences between the words novelty and innovation. Innovation is the latest achievements, knowledge, methods in this science. 13 These achievements, knowledge, methods become innovation when applied in practice. Currently, graduates of all higher education institutions are strictly required to:

- 1) they are modern computer and information technologies;
- 2) must be fluent in foreign languages, especially English.

In this regard, revision and improvement of educational programs based on the specificity of each educational direction is envisaged. In order to make it easier for students to use international educational resources, a modern fiber-optic single computer network will be launched in the coming years for higher education institutions. With the help of this high-speed Internet network, it will be possible to communicate with educational institutions of our country and abroad, and conduct video conferences. The decree of the head of our state dated June 12, 2015 "On measures to further improve the system of retraining and professional development of managers and pedagogues of higher education institutions" to raise the work in this regard to a new level, professors of higher educational institutions It is extremely important as it aims to fundamentally improve the quality of training of highly qualified specialists based on the introduction of an improved system of regular retraining of teachers in accordance with modern requirements. In the decree, the important directions of retraining and further improvement of the system of professional development of the management and pedagogic personnel of higher education institutions were determined. In particular, with the wide introduction of high-performance modern education and innovation technologies, advanced foreign experience, to fundamentally update the qualification requirements, curricula, programs and methods of retraining and improving the qualifications of pedagogic staff of higher educational institutions. related measures were expressed. This, in turn, is a necessary condition for professors and teachers teaching students in higher educational institutions to keep up with the times, to widely introduce innovations in 14 subjects, as well as advanced methods into the educational process. creates conditions, and at the same time requires continuous development of professional skills, pedagogical and scientific activities. After all, educating the young generation coming of age with intellectual potential and intelligence, providing them with pure knowledge is directly related to the high level of knowledge of specialists. According to the decree, it is necessary to organize retraining and professional development courses for leaders and pedagogues of higher educational institutions, which are constantly operating in the relevant areas of retraining, and to conduct training in these courses at a high-quality organizational and professional level. it was noted that it is necessary to form a teaching-methodical and material-technical base. These efforts, of course, in the conditions of today's market economy, will help to train highly qualified and mature specialists, make the higher education system literally an important factor in the socio-economic life of the country,

and also increase the quality and efficiency of the personnel training system. . Based on the above, we will consider some methods that can be used in the educational process of the higher education system. Modular-credit system and Blended learning Modular technologies are the most modern technology, based on the systematic processing and analysis of information made up of module blocks, based on the independent activity of the student, using various forms in the diagnosis of knowledge, skills and competencies. process. The module is a didactically designed, result-oriented unit with a meaningful and logical end, consisting of input and output controls. A modular program is a set of module blocks within one discipline, a set of didactic goals to be achieved, methods and tools used. A training module is a relatively independent, logically completed part of a training course. It consists of educational methodical support, theoretical and practical parts, parts such as assignment and current and final control. 15 Blended learning is a mixed education system and is an educational concept, which independently learns knowledge online and in the daytime with the participation of a teacher, that is, the meaning of "here and now" is understood. . Brick and Mortar is an English idiom that means traditional. Therefore, Brick and Mortar Education is a traditional form of full-time education. In this case, the computer serves as a mediator in education. Forms of mixed education:

- Blended learning; Hubrid learning;
- Technology-Mediated Instruction;
- Web-Enhanced Instruction;
- Mixed-Model Instruction.

It existed in the 60s of the 20th century, and in 1999, the concept was changed to EPIC Learning by the Interactive Learning Center of the American press. In their report, it was recommended to teach through the Internet. The use of blended learning methodology was taken into account. In 2006, Bonk and Graham's book highlighted face-to-face and computer-based teaching. In 1998, Alexander McKenzie's study noted the ease of computer-assisted learning of BKM. Blended learning consists of three parts:

- Distance learning (Distance learning);
- Teaching in the classroom (Face - To - Face learning);

Online learning Advantages: knowledge collection and evaluation, and the teacher can teach many people. Disadvantages: Blended learning models by act:

- Face-To-Face Driver (Driver Daytime Education)
- Rotation Model (Rotation Model)

Flex Model (Flexible model) 16

Online Lab • Self-Blend Model

Online Driver Model (Driver online education) Case study and distance learning Case study was used in Harvard University in 1870 and later in 1920 in Harvard Business School. The typology of cases is divided according to the main sources, the presence of a plot, the consistency of the situation statement in time, the object of the case, the method of presenting the material, its volume, structural character, the method of presenting the educational task, the didactic purpose, the method of presentation. Steps to implement the case method:

Introduction to the case;

Identify the main problem;

Gathering and searching for ideas;

Analyzing the ideas that recommended the solution of the case;

Case solution and recommendations

References:

1. Murodullaevich, M. N., & Sharifjanovna, Q. M. (2023). The role of information systems in the management structure. INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF RESEARCH IN COMMERCE, IT, ENGINEERING AND SOCIAL SCIENCES ISSN: 2349-7793 Impact Factor: 6.876, 17(01), 18-21.
2. Murodullaevich, M. N., & Sharifjanovna, Q. M. (2023). STAGES OF INTRODUCTION OF ELECTRONIC GOVERNMENT. INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF RESEARCH IN COMMERCE, IT, ENGINEERING AND SOCIAL SCIENCES ISSN: 2349-7793 Impact Factor: 6.876, 17(01), 15-17.
3. Murodullaevich, M. N., & Sharifjanovna, Q. M. (2023). Methodological bases of educational process information. ASIA PACIFIC JOURNAL OF MARKETING & MANAGEMENT REVIEW ISSN: 2319-2836 Impact Factor: 7.603, 12(01), 29-31.
4. Маллабоев, Н. М., & Боқижанов, Д. Д. (2022). КОМПЬЮТЕР ЖИНОЯТЧИЛИГИ ТУРЛАРИ ВА ЙЎНАЛИШЛАРИ. Экономика и социум, (6-2 (97)), 500-504.
5. Mallaboyev, N. M., Sharifjanovna, Q. M., & Nodirbek, M. (2022, May). INTERACTION BETWEEN INFORMATION COMPLEXES IN ECONOMIC SPHERES. In Conference Zone (pp. 250-253).
6. Mallaboyev, N. M., Sharifjanovna, Q. M., Muxammadjon, Q., & Shukurullo, C. (2022, May). INFORMATION SECURITY ISSUES. In Conference Zone (pp. 241-245).
7. Bulturbayevich, M. B. (2021). Challenges of Digital Educational Environment. Academic Journal of Digital Economics and Stability, 4, 54-60.

8. Pulatova, X. X., Mallaboev, N. M., & Akbarov, B. X. (2021). CLASSIFICATION OF ECONOMIC MATHEMATICAL MODELS. Экономика и социум, (4-1), 293-295.
9. Bulturbayevich, M. B., Rahmat, A., & Murodullayevich, M. N. (2021). Improving Teacher-Student Collaboration And Educational Effectiveness By Overcoming Learning Challenges. Aksara: Jurnal Ilmu Pendidikan Nonformal, 7(1), 153-160.
10. Mallaboev, N. M., Pulatova, X. X., & Akbarov, B. X. (2021). APPLICATION OF MATHEMATICAL MODELING IN SOLVING ECONOMIC PROBLEMS. Экономика и социум, (4-1), 190-194.
11. Mamurova, F. T., Abdullayeva, N. K., & Mallaboyev, N. (2019). USING THE «ASSESSMENT» METHOD IN ASSESSING STUDENTS KNOWLEDGE. Theoretical & Applied Science, (11), 80-83.
12. Holmirzaev, I. A., & Mallaboev, N. M. (2019). JOINT EDUCATIONAL EDUCATIONAL WORK OF THE TEACHER AND STUDENT AND METHODS OF IMPROVING THE QUALITY OF EDUCATION. Экономика и социум, (6 (61)), 49-53.
13. Маллабоев, Н., & Шокиров, Д. (2018). Роль стандарта в производстве качественных и безопасных продуктов. Экономика и социум, (5 (48)), 773-775.
14. Abdullayeva, O., & Mallaboyev, N. (2018). PROCESS OF STUDENT SELF-EDUCATION AND ITS DESIGN. Scientific Journal of Polonia University, 27(2), 116-119.
15. Маллабоев, Н., Имамназаров, Э., & Абдуллаева, Н. (2018). Перспективы производства продуктов питания. Экономика и социум, (5 (48)), 770-773.
16. Маллабоев, Н., & Шокиров, Д. (2016). ИННОВАЦИОННЫЕ ТЕХНОЛОГИИ В ФОРМИРОВАНИИ КАЧЕСТВА КОНКУРЕНТОСПОСОБНЫХ ОДАРЕННОЙ МОЛОДЕЖИ. Теория и практика современной науки, (6-1), 838-842.
17. Маллабоев, Н., & Шокиров, Д. (2016). СПОСОБЫ ОБЕСПЕЧЕНИЯ ИНФОРМАЦИОННОЙ БЕЗОПАСНОСТИ. Теория и практика современной науки, (6-1), 826-830.
18. Маллабоев, Н., & Абдуллаева, Н. (2016). МЕСТО СИСТЕМЫ" ЭЛЕКТРОННОГО ПРАВИТЕЛЬСТВА" В РАЗВИТИИ МАЛОГО БИЗНЕСА И ПРЕДПРИНИМАТЕЛЬСТВА. Теория и практика современной науки, (6-1), 834-838.

POLAND

CURRENT APPROACHES AND NEW RESEARCH IN MODERN SCIENCES

International scientific-online conference

POLAND

19. Маллабоев, Н., & Шокиров, Д. (2016). СИСТЕМЫ ЭЛЕКТРОННОГО ПЛАТЕЖА. Теория и практика современной науки, (6-1), 830-834.
20. Fotima, N., Nosirjon, M., & Alisher, A. (2015). Development of an electronic educational-methodical complex and using in educational process. Austrian Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences, (1-2), 76-77.
21. Nurdinova, F., Mallaboev, N., & Anvarov, A. (2015). Development of an electronic educational-methodical complex and using in educational process. Austrian Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences, (1-2), 76-77.
22. Райимжанова, Н., Носиржон, М., & Алишер, А. (2015). Рекомендации по самопознание и саморазвитие для обеспечение духовного развитие студентов ВУЗа. Austrian Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences, (1-2), 74-76.
23. Anvarov, A., & Mallaboev, N. (2015). Methods for Effective education. Scientific Journal Yan Kochanovski University, Poland, 3(4).
24. Matlubahon, K., Mukarramxon, K., & Alisher, A. (2015). Role of the international cooperation in high education development. Austrian Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences, (1-2), 72-73.
25. Mallaboyev, N. M., & Sharifjanovna, Q. M. Elmurod G 'ayratjon o 'g, U., & Najmiddin Ulug 'bek o 'g, T.(2022, May). TRENDS IN THE SPEED OF INTERNATIONAL INFORMATION NETWORKS. In Conference Zone (pp. 246-249).
26. Anvarov, A. (2015). Recommendations on self-cognition and self development for ensuring spiritual development of students University. Austrian Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences, 1(1-2), 74-75.

